

Interview guide

Defining Security Debt: A Case Study Based On Practice

Section	Question
Consent	Introduction about the study and what we will be talking about.
Consent	Documenting consent before the interview starts.
Introduction	Tell me a little bit about the project you are working on (team size, project duration, roles, etc.)
TD	How do you think of TD?
TD	Do you have an example of a TD item?
SD	When you hear the term SD what do you think of?
SD	Do you have an example of a SD item?
SD	How is SD different from security vulnerabilities?
SD	Are there security vulnerabilities that are not SD and vice versa?
Conclusion	Send an email to the interviewee with additional contact information in case there is something they want to add or if they have questions